

COBOTS IMPLEMENTATION IN REHABILITATION PROCESS

David LUPU¹, Süleyman Toraşan², Adrian Pîslă³

PhD Student¹, PhD Student², Prof., PhD³

Technical University of Cluj-Napoca

Design Engineering and Robotics Department, Industrial Engineering, Robotics and

Production Management Faculty, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca,

103-105 Muncii Avenue, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

lupu.david97@yahoo.com¹, sueleyman.torasan@hfwu.de², adrian.pisla@muri.utcluj.ro³

<http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *The aim of the presented research is about the needs identification for implementing rehabilitation robotics and some requirements for an effective implementation.*

Methodology/approach – *Through an initial bibliographic study, conducted by interrogation specialized, but accessible, databases to find the most considered robotic systems dedicated for rehabilitation, leading to an adequate centralized synthesis.*

Findings – *The considered result shows that most applied upper limb rehabilitation robots, implemented in clinics, but used mostly in clinical studies. Furthermore, was identified that the type of clinical used training mode is dedicated to the predominant employed joint. The components dedicate to the data analysis, the ones used by the robot and the ones used within robot assisted rehabilitation applications, were also processed for a centralized overview.*

Research limitations/implications – *At this stage, the conducted research implies only data available in English, German and Romanian languages, with the examples from these languages covering area.*

Practical implications – *The practical use of research refers to the identification of a possible practical approach for implementing new robotic systems for assisted rehabilitation within specialized clinics and then to increase the number and the quality of the robotic rehabilitation procedures.*

Originality/value – *The up to now original funding shows that robotic therapy may benefit from more date that displays reasons that facilitates the rise of the robotic rehabilitation usage, and the new addressability based on the increase in neurologic burden in parallel with the decreased number of qualified personnel/1000 patients. At the same time, the paper tackled partially the technological developments, financial dimension and administrative issues that are hindering a larger implementation.*

Key words: *Cobots, Rehabilitation, Robotic assisted rehabilitation*

Acknowledgement: This research has been supported by the project New frontiers in adaptive modular robotics for patient-centred medical rehabilitation - ASKLEPIOS, funded by European Union—NextGenerationEU and Romanian Government, under National Recovery and Resilience Plan for Romania, contract no. 760071/23.05.2023, code CF 121/15.11.2022, with Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization, within Component 9, investment I8.

Introduction

Medical rehabilitation involves the recovery of a person to the highest possible physical, psychological, social, vocational, professional and educational potential in accordance with the deficit caused by the condition and the limitations that may arise as a result.

Rehabilitation includes the maximization of physical capacity, preventing deterioration due to secondary illnesses, the optimization of the patient's environment, facilitating psychological adaptation to disability, and encouraging social reintegration. The robots (Cobots) that can be included in the rehabilitation process, are defined by a dynamic mechatronic system that provides physical and informational assistance during therapy sessions for the rehabilitation of sensorimotor deficits caused by central nervous system, peripheral nervous system, or musculoskeletal system impairments, or for assistance in daily life activities.

Through these two mechanisms, robotic rehabilitation and conventional rehabilitation, a multidisciplinary team can positively contribute to the patient's quality of life improvement by increasing independence and functionality. During the rehabilitation process, individuals undergo all three processes outlined in the ICF model implemented by the World Health Organization: MPS – the motor, the psychological, and the social process. Like most of the research teams, we recognize that the obtained results may describe only a sort of early phase of the assisted robotic rehabilitation implementation, where the technological solutions introduced by Industry 4.0 have not reached their full potential and have not compensated for the encountered rehabilitation deficiencies related to their use. (Asia-pacific-rehabilitation-robots-market, 2021)

Figure 1. Biopsychosocial model of care

General Types of Robots used in Rehabilitation Process

Robots intended for assisted rehabilitation, are actually Cobots - Robots designed to work alongside humans and not instead or isolated from humans -, that can be classified into two categories based on their intended role:

1. Segment recovery robots
2. Segment compensation robots

In the recovery purposes, the role of the robotic device is defined as restoring the individual's ability to perform tasks using previously used movements. For compensatory purposes, the role of the robotic device can involve atypical approaches to meet task requirements, and using alternative mechanisms that are not commonly

used by a person. The considered devices can be of the following types: prostheses, orthoses, or complementary rehabilitation systems:

- A. A prosthesis is an artificial replacement for a missing limb.
- B. An orthosis is an external device aimed at stabilizing movement or protecting the affected segment.
- C. Complementary systems for rehabilitation include systems or devices controlled by the physiotherapist or by the patient's still-functional components.

Segmentation of the Robotic Assisted Therapy Applications

A. Assistance in therapy clinics

For the robot-assisted interventions, that refers to the conventional therapy modes used in clinical practice and characterizing the patient's state during interaction. three main types of physical human-robot interaction applications have been defined: the Passive, Assisted, and the Active.

In the Passive mode application, the Cobot performs all kinematic-dynamic activities, independent from the patient's response, but in direct monitoring with the patient's condition.

In the Assisted mode application, the patient's voluntary activity is required at all times throughout the therapy movements, while the Cobot provide assistance only in completing the performance of the tasks.

In the Active mode application, the Cobot is used as a "*movement parameters measuring device*". Performance results solely from the patient's contribution, based on the defined three working types:

- The A: "**active**", basic type - the system does not provide mechanical work to the patient's limb.
- The AA: "**active-assisted**" type – the system assistance for completing tasks is offered only when the patient is unable to perform them.
- The R: "**resistive**" type - the Cobot is generating an opposing force to the movement, to increase the patient capability.

In therapy clinics, robotic assisted systems could be used in the process of assessing capabilities, providing precise and neutral data on evaluated movements range and angles. This can help both the patient and the therapist.

In case of re-evaluation, the evolution and specific differences for a considered period of time can be objectively highlighted, leading to the optimization of the rehabilitation process and the evaluation procedures, increasing the well-being and optimism of patients.

B. Minor assistance at home

The specialized literature mention and describes various robotic systems intended to support ADLs (Activities of Daily Living), aiming the increase of the living quality and ease the performing of daily activities, differentiated by the type of limb. (BROKAW et al., 2011)

For the upper limb, is exemplified the HandSOME (Europe Rehabilitation robots Market, 2021) glove, which helps for the patient's hand opening and the extension of the finger movements.

HandSOME uses a series of elastic cords and springs to apply the extension moment to the finger joint, together with adjustable stoppers as a safety measure to control the range of motion.

For the lower limb, "electric driven orthoses" are used, with a dual role in stabilizing the lower limb functionality and assisting in the locomotion process.

C. Assistance with ADLs

In the cases where the patient cannot go down the stairs and the location does not have the possibility of a ramp, a lift attached to the handrail can be used. Transfer with the help of robots, such as the Robot for Interactive Body Assistance (RIBA) – developed by the RIKEN-SRK Center for Human-Interactive Robot Research and Sumitomo Riko Company in Japan – transfers patients by lifting them from the bed or wheelchair to new positions. (Diaz, Gil, and Sanchez, 2011)

The global status of rehabilitation dedicated Cobots

According to the Market Analysis Report, the global rehabilitation robots' market was valued at USD 226.0 million in 2021 and is expected to expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 17.3% from 2022 to 2030. Rehabilitation Robots Market Size & Share Report, 2022-2030. (Machando, 2023)

Considering their applicability, rehabilitation robots are predominantly used for lower limb pathologies compared to upper limb pathologies. Among the reasons cited are the ease of the rehabilitation process for the lower limb, which has a much lower degree of complexity compared to the upper limb, the much more easily appreciated recovery speed visibility for the lower limb, and not least, the fact that there is a much larger bibliography in the specialized literature presenting studies showing the increased efficacy of lower limb rehabilitation compared to the upper limb. From an anatomical and physiological standpoint, another reason is the motor engram held at the cerebral level, an engram dedicated to functional motor processes. In this engram, the brain has a larger "imprint" on some segments (the hand) compared to others (the foot). The engram can be affected by various pathologies but can also be modified through neuroplasticity with the help of rehabilitation.

Factors contributing to the rise of robotic rehabilitation

- Development of intelligent robotic systems capable of adapting to provide personalized multimodal therapies for patients with neuromotor deficits.
- The increasing prevalence of central nervous system pathologies (such as stroke, Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis) as indicated by the Asklepios team (Khan, Siddique, and Lee, 2020), along with the rise in orthopedic, cardiovascular, and endocrine pathologies.
- An insufficiency in qualified personnel, that have to be compensated

Region	Population	Prevalence of neurological diseases	Deaths due to neurological disease	DALYs	Number of neurologists ³	Number of EAN associate members
European Union (EU28)	512,355,000	307,859,199	1116,038	21,046,899	43,306	19,166
Western Europe	432,969,000	260,827,756	892,162	16,499,342	36,009	15,465
Central Europe	114,803,000	67,368,506	300,317	6,024,036	9,031	5,529
Eastern Europe	210,199,000	130,372,328	604,144	13,110,119	29,016	11,024
WHO Region Europe	925,631,000	542,935,521	1,981,463	41,319,938	83,397	35,798

Figure 2 insufficiency in qualified personnel in relation to neurologists

- The growing geriatric population coupled with an increase in injuries. The rising prevalence of pathologies is the dominant factor driving the development of rehabilitation technologies. According to the WHO (Musculoskeletal Conditions. WHO, 2022), in 2021, there were approximately 1.71 billion people globally suffering from musculoskeletal disorders. This growing number of individuals with such conditions results in the necessity of using rehabilitation robots for physical, psychological, or social conditions.
- Presently, the Asia Pacific region represents the fastest-growing market in the utilization of rehabilitation robots. The aging societies in the Asia-Pacific region, particularly Japan and China, are driving the growth of the medical technology sector, thereby creating a huge market for rehabilitation robots. (Maciejasz, P. et al., 2014)
- In the North America region, the increasing prevalence of spinal cord injuries fuels the growth of the rehabilitation robot's market. The growing geriatric and disabled populations are among the factors driving the adoption of rehabilitation robots. (Rehabilitation-robots-market, 2024)
- In the European region, the aging population and the increasing cases of myocardial infarction, stroke, and spinal cord injuries propel the rehabilitation robot market in Europe. Heart attack and stroke, being major causes of death among the elderly population, often lead to disabilities requiring rehabilitation, with many patients suffering from chronic conditions requiring continuous attention and care. (Rehabilitation Robots Market Size & Share Report, 2022-2030)

The global implementation status of upper limb robotic rehabilitation

Following the bibliographic study conducted through online accessible databases from December 2023 to February 2024, 132 robotic systems dedicated to the upper limb were identified, for which a dataset was centralized, leading to the following conclusions:

Most of the robotic systems were developed in the United States of America, and not all of them are available on other continents, with some not even available in the regions where they were implemented for study purposes. This is true for certain systems in Europe or Asia as well. This aspect is justified by various reasons such as price, testing stage, and lack of clinical evidence of effectiveness.

The predominant focus segment is the elbow joint, as it is a "hinge" joint with a single degree of freedom, performing only flexion and extension movements, making the implementation of a robotic system at this level much simpler. The thumb is the least involved in robotic systems due to the complexity of movements, especially opposition and types of grips.

The predominant training mode is passive-active, allowing patients to initiate the movement and then the robot to continue it. The inclusion of multiple types of training in recently built rehabilitation robots has been observed, thus diversifying rehabilitation, and the robots can more easily adapt to the patients' needs.

The predominantly analyzed data by the robotic systems were the range of motion, force, and velocity. Few of them considered coordination or spasticity, but there is not an standardized accepted method for evaluation.

The global implementation status of lower limb robotic rehabilitation

In an article (Inaki, 2011), 43 lower limb rehabilitation robots were identified, half of which were not available on the market. The reasons cited were similar to those found for the upper limb robots: high costs, lack of clinical evidence, and the need for a well-implemented protocol.

The status of robotic implementation in Romania

During the article's development, an investigation into the situation in Romania was conducted, particularly through the analysis of official data posted online and accessible databases, supplemented by information gathered from the network of active doctoral students. As a result, the following information regarding rehabilitation centers with robotic rehabilitation services could be centralized:

Bucharest

- University Hospital offers a website discussing robotic rehabilitation, without being able to identify information about their actual use within the hospital.
- Hipocrat Medical Clinic uses the "G-EO Evolution" robotic system for gait rehabilitation, a system used in neurological and orthopedic conditions.

Cluj-Napoca

- Kinetoteam uses a robotic system for the evaluation and functional training of static and dynamic balance.
- MedicCover Hospital offers patients the possibility to use the "Lokomat" system, a robotic exoskeleton for gait re-education for patients with motor deficits to regain lower limb functions.

Iași

- Arcadia Medical Recovery Hospital has the most diverse range of rehabilitation robots (Rehabilitation Robots Market Size & Share Report, 2022-2030): Lokomat; Andago, for gait rehabilitation; Armeo Spring, an exoskeleton for upper limb rehabilitation, treatment, or active training to increase mobility, muscle strength, control, and coordination; Indego, a modular exoskeleton for regaining and retraining ground walking.
- Iasi Clinical Recovery Hospital - the website describes various robotic systems, exoskeletons, and upper limb rehabilitation systems (without specifications).

Târgu Mureș

- Hyperbarichospital implements a robotic exoskeleton system for lower limb rehabilitation services.
- OFK Medical Center uses the Kineo robotic system for medical treatment and rehabilitation and lower limb training, as well as the "Alter G" anti-gravity treadmill, which can reduce body weight by up to 100%, allowing athletes or patients to start rehabilitation much earlier.

Timișoara

- No clinic implementing robotic systems was identified.

The rehabilitation robots used in the mentioned clinics are predominantly for the lower limb, and the pathologies for which they are used are neurological (stroke) and orthopedic (fractures).

Requirements, demands and barriers for implementation

Both regionally and internationally, robotic rehabilitation systems are continuously evolving, focusing more on the active component of movements, involving increased patient participation in rehabilitation. The integration of multiple body segments by the robotic system assists patients in their daily activities, thereby facilitating their reintegration into social environments.

SWOT Analysis Regarding the Implementation of Rehabilitation Robots

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administering rehabilitation for multiple patients • Collecting data through objective methods • Assisting with the patient's daily activities • Enhanced precision and consistency in therapy delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of technologies • Lack of resources for in-depth research in the field • Absence of in-hospital testing • Requirement for specialized training for healthcare professionals to operate and manage the robots effectively
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting systems to different symptoms, such as tremors in Parkinson's disease • Using robotic systems at patients' homes • Integrating multiple body segments in rehabilitation • Growing demand for innovative rehabilitation technologies, driven by an aging population and increasing prevalence of chronic conditions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although accidents were not mentioned during the studies, they can occur due to errors from the rehabilitation robotic system • Patients' dependence on the robotic system may lead to a decrease in achieving independence • Lack of motivation from either the patient or the therapist • Economic uncertainties and budget constraints within healthcare systems, potentially limiting investment in robotic technologies.

To make robotic-assisted rehabilitation much more accessible and tailored, several measures are proposed:

1. Using robots in various motor phases of the body, not just in standing.

Most of the robots are used only in favorable positions for the patient (sitting, standing). Some robotic orthoses could be integrated to increase independence in bed turns or lifting from bed, then the orthosis could be used while sitting and then standing. An adaptable rehabilitation robot to the body position and not just situational.

2. Using robotized structures that are easy to assemble and use.

Developing synergy and collaboration between the rehabilitation team professionals and designers, with the realization of shared projects and properly designed.

3. Applying standardized protocols

The implementation of standardized protocols specifying the objectives of the rehabilitation process, with a well-defined assessment at its core, demonstrating both quality of life and daily functionality, and a rehabilitation involving everyday activities.

4. Improving the stability, agility, and resistance of movements, so that the system is:

- More agile and faster, by increasing relative strength capacity and reaction speed.
- More stable against disturbances, by modulating the sensorimotor response of the neuromuscular system.
- More robust, by dissipating mechanical energy to prevent injury during high-impact activities.

5. Operator safety is one of the most important requirements when implementing rehabilitation robots, as the operating staff, medical practitioners and the patients are in close proximity with the robot. As the operators of rehabilitation robots are medical practitioners and not engineers, these robots need to be easy to handle, operate and maintain (Khan et al., 2020)

6. In terms of power requirements these depend on the robot utilized and the hospital they are implemented in. In general, constant access to power should be ensured to recharge the robot, however in field hospitals renewable energy sources are also used for operating medical robots. A solution currently under development is the wireless power transfer, which would minimize the need to charge the robot (Khan et al., 2020)

7. The cost factor is a further requirement to be considered at implementation, with the author stating that for a large-scale deployment of robotic solutions in the healthcare sector the robots need to be affordable (for developing countries as well) (Khan et al., 2020)

To make these improvements, engineers will need to continue the redesign of the robot's structure, physiologists will need to refine human performance evaluation, physiotherapists will need to consider how different systems can further rehabilitation interventions, psychologists will need to better understand how technology interacts with and embodies the user, and designers will need to consider the robot's creation plan.

Conclusion

From what has been outlined, it emerges that robot-mediated treatments need to be studied, leading to the development of new methods and procedures for appropriately stimulating the factors that compose the nature of movement. Therefore, an interdisciplinary rehabilitation process could consider the physical, psychological, and social deficits of the patient, generating a corresponding protocol in approaching robotic therapy, a protocol composed both in the use of complementary systems and in the approach of conventional physiotherapy.

As can be seen, robotic rehabilitation is continuously growing, and unfortunately, the prevalence of pathologies is also on the rise. There is a need for an increasing number of electronic devices for assessment and interventions in the healthcare domain. More efficient rehabilitation services are necessary, and technology can provide improved assessment and monitoring accuracy, facilitating independent practice and self-management. Clinical adaptation is limited, and factors influencing the use of rehabilitation technology are still underexploited. Both regionally and internationally, robotic rehabilitation systems are continuously evolving, and we should pay attention to the functional needs of patients, strengthen multidisciplinary communication and cooperation, and promote rehabilitation robots to better serve the rehabilitation medical field.

References

Asia-pacific-rehabilitation-robots-market

2021

Available at <https://www.theinsightpartners.com/reports/asia-pacific-rehabilitation-robots-market>

BROKAW et al.

2011

"Hand Spring Operated Movement Enhancer (HandSOME): A Portable Passive Hand Exoskeleton for Stroke Rehabilitation" in E. B. Brokaw, I. Black, R. J. Holley and P. S. Lum (eds.), IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering, 19:391-399

Europe Rehabilitation robots Market

2021

Available at <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5416540/europe-rehabilitation-robots-market-forecast-to>

Inaki Diaz , Jorge Juan Gil, and Emilio Sanchez

2011

"Lower-Limb Robotic Rehabilitation:Literature Review and Challenges" in Doyoung Jeon (eds.), Journal of robotics

Machando, J.

2023

"New frontiers in adaptive modular robotics for patient-centered medical rehabilitation" available at <https://cester.utcluj.ro/asklepios/index.php/en/>

Khan, Z. H., Siddique, A., and Lee, C. W.

2020

Robotics Utilization for Healthcare Digitization in Global COVID-19 Management. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 17(11), 3819.

Maciejasz, P. et al.

2014

"A survey on robotic devices for upper limb rehabilitation." in Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation. Springer

Musculoskeletal Conditions. Who.int. World Health Organization: WHO

2022

Available at <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/musculoskeletal-conditions>.

Rehabilitation-robots-market

2024

Available at <https://www.researchnester.com/reports/rehabilitation-robots-market/4049>

Rehabilitation Robots Market Size & Share Report, 2022-2030

2022

Rehabilitation Robots Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Type (Therapy Robots, Exoskeleton), By Extremity (Upper Body, Lower Body), By End-use, By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2022 – 2030 available at <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/rehabilitation-robots-market-report>

RIBA robot

2011

Available at <http://rtc.nagoya.riken.jp/RIBA/index-e.html>.

Winstein C and Requejo P.

2015

“Innovative Technologies for Rehabilitation and Health Promotion: What Is the Evidence?” in Physical Therapy, 95(3):294–298. United Kingdom: Oxford Academic.